

Students Satisfaction Towards Global Learning Session as Collaborative Teaching and Learning Method

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 21 August 2022 Revised: 24 August 2022 Accepted: 27 August 2022 Published: 1 September 2022</p> <p>Keywords: Global Learning Higher Education Teaching and Learning Online Learning COVID-19</p> <p> OPEN ACCESS</p>	<p>Due to the COVID-19 outbreak in early 2020, the Malaysian government announced the Movement Control Order (MCO). This caused a sudden change in the academic sector from primary to higher education, to convert a traditional learning method to an online learning method. The initiative is taken to ensure the students still get their education, but it is challenging for educators to maintain the quality of the student's understanding. Thus, in this study, the aim is to explore the implementation of Global Learning Session (GLS) as one of the online learning methods. This study involves 57 undergraduate students from Universiti Teknologi MARA who took Calculus II subject. In this paper, the effectiveness of students' satisfaction with the Global Learning Session is presented, and it has proven to be helpful for students to enhance their knowledge and engage with international educators.</p>

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INTRODUCTION

The worldwide COVID-19 outbreak has created the largest disruption of all sectors including the education system, affecting all countries across the globe (Pokhrel and Chhetri, 2021). The virus was first identified in Wuhan, China in December 2019 and it has spread to all countries within a few months. Lockdown and staying home strategies have been put in place as the needed action to flatten the curve and control the transmission of the disease (Sintema, 2020). The spread of COVID-19 led to the closure of all education institutions all over the world. Hence, the online learning method is implemented to deliver, manage, and track courses over the internet. It involves the advance technology to facilitate two ways communication between students and educators.

Both students and educators are slowly adapting to the implementation of online learning methods, especially on the usage of recent technology. There are some challenges on online learning methods which are the lack of student-educator engagement, limited accessibility to internet, difficulty interacting with friends, and no laboratory access (Selvanathan et al., 2020). However, the online learning method is the only choice that we had during the pandemic, but until today, the education sector still practicing the online learning method to broaden the student's knowledge and experience through internationalization in education. Thus, the global learning session is introduced.

Global learning session brings international opportunities through Online Distance Learning (ODL). In line with Education 5.0, global learning provides a platform for educators and learners from all over the world to build international networks and improve teaching and learning experiences by conducting global learning sessions. This is also in line with the university's aspiration to provide a world-class education as well as to produce well-balanced, entrepreneurial graduates who are globally competent (CiDL, 2022). In addition, Education 5.0 at Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) has five core areas to be concentrated on, which are learning that goes beyond good grades on campus, personalisation and personalized learning experience, design a space to learn and to create, provision of challenging tasks and content, and inculcation of a value-based learning culture. Hence, the global learning session is believed to have contributed to the Education 5.0.

In this study, the teaching method has undergone some innovation, where global learning session is implemented and had been used to conduct one of the classes of Calculus II subject. This session is useful for the students to engage with an international collaborator, experience global learning, and explore new knowledge.

In the next section, the implementation of global learning session in Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM) is presented.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Implementation of Global Learning Session

A collaborative teaching and learning method are widely used among educators in higher education and has been practiced by education institutions in some countries since 1990 (McDaniel and Colarulli, 1997). According to McDaniel and Colarulli, the purposes of collaborative teaching are to develop more curricular coherence for students, to reduce the fragmentation of the curriculum, to stimulate learning across disciplines, and/or to motivate students to learn by associating with their peers. The educators or lecturers are co-teaching where lecturers work together to plan lessons, teach, monitor students' progress and manage the class (Clarke and Kinuthia, 2009).

During the pandemic, collaborative teaching and learning are done virtually. Rapid developments in technology have made it easy which offers the possibility to learn anywhere and anytime (Dhawan, 2020). In 2014, Wiegant et al. explored and stressed the value of collaborative teaching and learning in undergraduate biology courses. The students are divided into groups during the learning process and Linton et al. (2014) found that the students in a group setting have better conceptual understanding compared to an individual setting. According to research, the effectiveness of student discussions in cooperative learning groups depends

on their ability to argue (Teasley, 1995; Chinn et al., 2000), clarify their ideas to one another (Veenman et al., 2005), and incorporate and expand on one another's ideas (Barron, 2003). It is believed that these peer connections will aid in students' cognitive reorganisation (Webb, 2009).

However, UiTM has set seven types of models for the lecturers to choose to implement collaborative teaching, which is represented in Table 1 (CiDL, 2022).

Table 1 : UiTM's collaborative teaching models

Model 1	Content Development
Model 2	Delivery
Model 3	Evaluation Assessment
Model 4	Content Development and Delivery
Model 5	Content Development and Evaluation Assessment
Model 6	Delivery and Evaluation of Assessment
Model 7	Content Development, Delivery and Evaluation of Assessment

Global Learning Session (GLS) focuses on delivery model, where the lecturer invites an international speaker to deliver a sharing session on any topic related to the class syllabus. It can be either to give better understanding of the class syllabus or share some new knowledge that the students do not learn in the class.

The session is conducted virtually to practice Online Distance Learning (ODL) and it is more flexible for both speaker and the students to attend from anywhere. It is also cost-effective. During the session, the speaker delivered her sharing on a part of application in Calculus II subject and gave some examples for the students to understand better. Then, the students are allowed to ask any questions related to the talk.

The usage of virtual platform that is used for the GLS is explained in the next section.

The Usage of Virtual Platform

The COVID-19 outbreak has triggered a notable change in education. As most parts of the world were locked down, virtual platforms are the best option to have discussions, meetings, seminars, workshops, and training. Various online platforms such as Cisco Webex, Zoom, Google Meet, and Microsoft Teams grow at a rapid rate. To conduct the GLS, the Cisco Webex with license is chosen to accommodate at most 1000 capacity without time restriction. Besides that, it also provides unlimited cloud space for meeting recordings, can join overlapping meetings at the same time, assign one or more cohosts to manage the meeting, and live polling during meeting. Webex Meeting is specifically designed for video conferencing and online events (Muniandi and Mohd Saad, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

GLS is implemented in Calculus II subject to give the student exposure to the real applications in advanced research and real-world problem, of the topic in the subject. Other than that, the other objective of organizing GLS is to give an opportunity to the students to engage with the international speaker. Indirectly, this also enhances their communication skills and confidence level. This study is implemented on 57 undergraduate students, 21 of whom are from the Civil Engineering course and the rest are from the Electrical Engineering course, who took Calculus II subject. The percentage of attendance is presented as follows.

Figure 1: Percentage of students' attendance

In this study, a quantitative approach is done as data collection via questionnaires where the feedback forms are distributed to all the participants. The feedback forms are divided into two instruments; A and B. A is the respondent's demography while B is the student's satisfaction with the Global Learning Session. Five-point Likert scale; poor, fair, satisfactory, good, and excellent are used in the feedback forms to identify the respondent's satisfaction which leads to the effectiveness of GLS. The collected data from the feedback forms are recorded and analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 24.0. In SPSS, the five-point Likert scale is changed; poor (1), fair (2), satisfactory (3), good (4), and excellent (5).

The descriptive analysis of the collected data is stated in the following section.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the feedback form, seven items have been asked regarding the Global Learning Session, particularly related to the content and the technical part of the program. The mean and standard deviation are calculated to determine its effectiveness among students. The results obtained are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Students' satisfaction on Global Learning Session

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
Relevance of the topic with the subject	4.526	0.504
Content delivered	4.632	0.487
Speaker's knowledge regarding the topic	4.351	0.641
Contribution of GLS to learning/ new knowledge	4.474	0.504
Understandable of the material/ slide	4.404	0.496
Smoothness of the virtual platform	4.649	0.481
Clarity of the sound and speaker	4.561	0.501
Overall	4.514	0.525

Based on the results in Table 2, the item smoothness of virtual platform has the highest mean compared to others which is 4.649, followed by the content delivered (4.632), clarity of the sound and speaker (4.561), the topic of GLS is relevant to the subject (4.526), the GLS is contribute the learning and new knowledge (4.474), the material is easy to understand (4.404) and the speaker's knowledge (4.351).

In addition, the standard deviation of each item is also found to measure how dispersed the data is in relation to the mean. Low standard deviation means data are clustered around the mean, and high standard deviation means the data are more spread out. According to Table 2, the standard deviation of all items is low, which are in the range of 0.45 to 0.55. This shows that the respondents are satisfied with the Global Learning Session, where the data is around the mean. The main objectives of organizing GLS are achieved, which the session contributes to the students' new knowledge and conduct by an international collaborator.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study was conducted to examine the students' satisfaction towards Global Learning Session as a collaborative teaching and learning method, specifically for Calculus II subject in UiTM. In general, the feedback from students showed positive pleasure as the virtual platform used is very convenient, since the learning process can be done anywhere. In addition, GLS provides a platform to enhance students' learning skills and gain additional knowledge that may not be accessible in a practical classroom. On the other hand, students had the opportunity to engage with international educators which eventually will provide a bridge to them to have more outstanding networking as well as further collaboration in the future. Hence, this pipeline of networking will create exposure to global education learning and thus, contributes to Education 5.0. Based on the findings, it is strongly recommended that the GLS should be organized every year as the practice positively impacts the students.

REFERENCES

- [1] Barron, B. (2003). When Smart Groups Fail. *The journal of the learning sciences*, 12(3), 307-359. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327809jls1203_1
- [2] Centre for Innovative Delivery & Learning Development (CiDL). <https://cidl.uitm.edu.my/CG-Global-Learning.php>
- [3] Chinn, C. A., O'donnell, A. M., & Jinks, T. S. (2000). The structure of discourse in collaborative learning. *The Journal of Experimental Education*, 69(1), 77-97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220970009600650>
- [4] Clarke, P.A.J. & Kunithia, W. (2009). A Collaborative Teaching Approach: Views of a Cohort of Preservice Teachers in Mathematics and Technology Courses. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, 21(1), 1-12.
- [5] Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A Panacea in the Time of COVID-19 Crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49(1), 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>
- [6] Linton, D. L., Farmer, J. K., & Peterson, E. (2014). Is Peer Interaction Necessary For Optimal Active Learning? *CBE—Life Sciences Education*, 13(2), 243-252. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.13-10-0201>
- [7] McDaniels, E. A., & Colarulli, G. C. (1997). Collaborative Teaching in the Face of Productivity Concerns: the Dispersed Team Mode. *Innovative Higher Education*, 22(1), 19-36.
- [8] Muniandi, M. & Mohd Saad, N.A. (2020). The Effectiveness of Google Meets, Blue Jeans, Cisco Webex and Zoom : The Students' Perception on the Distance Learning Support Tools. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 66(1), 12-19. <https://doi.org/10.47119/IJRP1006611220201597>
- [9] Pokhrel, S. & Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. *Higher Education for Future*, 8(1), 133-141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>
- [10] Selvanathan, M., Hussin, N. A. M., & Azazi, N. A. N. (2020). Students learning experiences during COVID-19: Work from home period in Malaysian Higher Learning Institutions. *Teaching Public Administration*, 1-10. <http://doi.org/10.1177/0144739420977900>
- [11] Sintema, E. J. (2020). Effect of COVID-19 on the performance of grade 12 students: Implications for STEM education. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(7). <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/7893>
- [12] Teasley, S. D. (1995). The Role of Talk in Children's Peer Collaborations. *Developmental psychology*, 31(2), 207. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.13-10-0201>
- [13] Veenman, S., Denessen, E., van den Akker, A., & Van Der Rijt, J. (2005). Effects of a Cooperative Learning Program on the Elaborations of Students During Help Seeking and Help Giving. *American Educational Research Journal*, 42(1), 115-151. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00028312042001115>
- [14] Webb, N. M. (2009). The Teacher's Role in Promoting Collaborative Dialogue in the Classroom. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 79(1), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709908x380772>
- [15] Wiegant FAC, Scager K, Peeters AJM, Boonstra J (2014). The challenge of writing a PhD proposal in honors (undergraduate) education: a group project as significant learning experience. In: *Pursuit of Excellence in a Networked Society: Theoretical and Practical Approaches Coming from the Conference Excellence in Higher Education and Beyond*, ed. MVC Wolfensberger, L Drayer, and JJM Volker, Munster, Germany: Waxmann, 77–84.